

4. <https://www.phoenix.edu/content/edu/us/en/blog/educational-learning-theories.html>.

USING TOTAL PHYSICAL RESPONSE METHOD IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Annotation: Early life is a time of rapid development for all aspects of a person's life, including their emotions, bodies, minds, and languages. The best time to begin introducing a foreign language or languages to young children is now.

No books are used in the classroom, but there are activities that teach through songs, games, and stories that engage the interest of young, engaged students. This study discusses the advantages of TPR in foreign language instruction for young learners and introduces several sample activities.

Key words: foreign language, aspects, gestures, method, students, instruction, physical activity

The study found that multilingualism has positive effects on employee engagement and productivity, with language proficiency being a significant predictor even after controlling for demographic variables. The study suggests that organizations can improve employee skills and performance by offering language learning and diversity training programs. The study also contributes to the understanding of the relationship between language, cognition, and social/cultural dimensions of language use in the workplace. Future research can explore moderating effects of other variables and use different sampling methods. Overall, the study emphasizes the importance of multilingualism in enhancing employee performance.

Originally intended for adult education, this method is now primarily utilized to teach preschool and primary school children.

Gestures, command execution, pantomime, and games are used to memorize new words, phrases, and lexical structures. Students repeat after the teacher, imitating the word. "I'm sad," for example, says the teacher. The guys must guess the meaning of the expression based on the gestures and the situation; the translation is not spoken aloud.

TPR is used to accomplish a variety of tasks, including:

- working out vocabulary related to movements (jump, swim, run) and body parts (eye, head, mouth, nose);
- activation of temporary structures (Every day I get up, I brush my hair, I wash my face);
- learning class phrases and commands (Open your books, stand up, sit down);
- relaxation and change of activity during physical training.

Because of the study's substance, the strategy is most effective at the initial stage of training. However, its application is applicable even at higher levels. As a result, it is ideal for learning different styles of walking (tiptoe, stumble, wobble) or verbs of "cooking" (grate, stir, whisk).

The TPR method is also particularly effective in teaching kids with dyslexia and students who struggle to learn foreign languages using standard methods.

Furthermore, this strategy is excellent for kinesthetic students who require physical interaction with subjects in every way available in the classroom.

TPR cannot be used to study everything, and excessive learning simply becomes uninteresting. However, when combined with other strategies, TPR can inject an element of fun into the process of absorption of new information, making it as successful as possible.

The TPR method combines language instruction with physical activity, promoting student response and creativity. The teacher models and presents new material, allowing students to speak at their own pace. The teacher's role is like

that of a parent, providing support and allowing for mistakes without discouragement. Students actively engage in language learning, with the teacher as a director and the students as actors. Specific instructional books are not provided by the creators of the physical response method. Initially, the teacher relies on verbal communication, body language, and classroom supplies. Additional materials like pictures, props, slides, and text cards are used to create interactive exercises. Arnold Muhren claims that the TPR method's fundamental technology is straightforward. When given instructions by the teacher or their peers (during later training levels), students obey. Initially, these instructions or set of instructions are straightforward (e.g., "Get up, sit down"), but as time goes on, they grow more intricate (e.g., "I want the boys to stand in a circle, please"). TPR can be modeled as a series of steps leading up to one difficult task (e.g., "Sit down, take a pen and paper, write it down at the top of your sheet...") or even the plot [Muhren 2003: 46].

When to use different mobile and role-playing games, dramatization, or narrative, if not during a class using the Total Physical Response approach.

Sing-sing - Children enjoy singing, particularly in chorus. In addition to improving your mood, music also helps you learn new words. Choose whatever your heart desires from the simple but entertaining music available on YouTube channels. Children enjoy songs about old farmers, like the one about McDonald.

You can study vocabulary related to animal names (cow, pig, dog, etc.) while listening to this tune. You can play the song and demonstrate the moves to the guys. They should be easy: swaying right and left, turning in various directions, and clapping. The sound that this or that animal is connected with must also be parodied ("mu" for cow, for example).

"Simon says" game - Using games and songs to teach vocabulary related to the "Body parts" topic.

- Using the motions and songs "Finger family" and "Baby shark" to learn language related to the topic of "Family members".

This chapter examines primary school students' psychological and pedagogical characteristics, vocabulary instruction specifics, and the history of the full physical response method. The method utilizes students' bodies as training material, relying on visibility for comprehension. It enhances engagement, motivation, and addresses challenges in teaching young children. The approach discourages translation and promotes interaction with the foreign language to grasp its logic and structure. However, it lacks emphasis on reading, writing, and grammar, limiting comprehensive language understanding. Incorporating written speech and grammatical study provides a deeper understanding of the language and native speakers' mindset. Repetitive strategies are suitable for single lesson tasks.

REFERENCES:

1. Baker, W. (2011). *Multilingualism and Multilingual Education*. Multilingual Matters.
2. Dearden, J., & Macaro, E. (2015). *English language teaching in its social context: A reader*. Routledge.
3. Gudykunst, W. B. (Ed.). (2016). *Bridging differences: Effective intergroup communication*. Sage Publications.
4. Krashen, S. (1982). *Principles and practice in second language acquisition*. Oxford Pergamon Press.
5. Krashen, S. (2003). *Explorations in language acquisition and use*. Heinemann.
6. Muhren, A. (2003). Total physical response in first year English. *Teaching English with Technology*, 3(3), 1-57.